

TOWARD REPRODUCIBLE MACHINE LEARNING PIPELINES IN HEALTHCARE APPLICATIONS

Ilija Tanasković^{1,2}, Nadica Miljković¹, Matija Zlatar³

1: University of Belgrade - School of Electrical Engineering, 11120, Belgrade, Serbia

2: The Institute for Artificial Intelligence Research and Development of Serbia, 21000, Novi Sad, Serbia

3: University of Belgrade - Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy, 11000, Belgrade, Serbia

e-mail: ilija.tanaskovic@ivi.ac.rs, nadica.miljkovic@etf.bg.ac.rs, matija.zlatar@ihtm.bg.ac.rs

Abstract

Computational reproducibility is a basic condition of trustworthy machine-learning research in healthcare, where model-based results may support decisions about human health, yet it is still frequently undermined by incomplete reporting of the source of the data, preprocessing, software environments, and evaluation procedures. This overview examines reproducibility across four stages of a typical machine-learning workflow: data source and accessibility, preprocessing and annotation, model development and training, as well as evaluation and validation. Using electrocardiogram analysis as a running example, the paper identifies common points at which computational reproducibility in healthcare is compromised, including restricted or poorly documented data access, hidden preprocessing choices, inconsistent annotation practices, untracked code and dependencies, uncontrolled pseudorandomness, data leakage, and insufficient external validation. Practical solutions are summarized from current literature, including transparent metadata, traceable curation, version-controlled and licensed code, portable computational environments, preserved model artefacts, benchmark evaluation, and rigorous reporting. Computational reproducibility is therefore presented not as an optional add-on, but as a continuous property of good scientific and clinical practice.

Keywords: computational reproducibility; machine learning; electrocardiography; biomedical signal processing; data curation; external validation

1 Introduction

Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) may be one of the most prevalent analytical methodologies currently utilized in healthcare and medical applications [1]. This rise has been driven by the growing availability of digital clinical data and by the ability of models to extract complex patterns from images, biomedical signals, and other high-dimensional data [2]. In electrocardiography (ECG), ML methods have already shown strong performance in clinically relevant tasks, such as arrhythmia detection from ambulatory ECG recordings [3] and automatic diagnosis from standard 12-lead ECG [4]. Consistently, recent reviews of ECG analysis indicate that DL, as a subset of ML¹, has become a major direction in the automated interpretation of cardiac signals, further confirming the importance of ML-based approaches in medicine, healthcare, and biomedical signal processing. [6].

¹Machine learning refers to computational methods that learn patterns from data, while deep learning is a subset of ML based on multi-layer neural networks [5].

However, the growing diagnostic and predictive power of ML models also makes the reliability of published computational results a central scientific issue. While computational reproducibility focuses on the recreation of results, reliability reflects the deeper trustworthiness and accuracy of the underlying models, which can only be achieved through thorough benchmarking against clinical reference data. A high reported accuracy is not sufficient if other researchers cannot reconstruct the workflow that produced that accuracy, verify the same result, or determine whether the result depends on hidden choices in data handling, preprocessing, software versions, or evaluation design [7, 8]. This problem is particularly important in healthcare applications, where diagnostic and decision-support systems are expected to provide stable and consistent outputs when the same patient data are analyzed under comparable conditions. In operational terms, poor computational reproducibility means that reported results may change because of differences in code, preprocessing, software environment, or insufficient methodological description, rather than because of true clinical differences. [7, 8, 9]

Before discussing these issues in detail, it should first be emphasized that computational reproducibility-related terminology is not used consistently across the literature, and that multiple definitions are currently in use. To clarify these distinctions within the context of this study, Figure 1 illustrates the foundational relationships between data and analysis workflows [10]. In this study, computational reproducibility is understood according to the definition used by Ziemann *et al.* [7], which focuses on obtaining the same computational results from the same data and code (Figure 1, top-left). Table 1 provides an overview of the major definitions and their corresponding sources. Among the related terms, replicability is commonly used to denote confirmation of the same scientific conclusion in an independent study based on newly acquired data (Figure 1, top-right). This distinction is useful because it separates rerunning the same workflow and confirming the conclusion beyond the original dataset. Furthermore, to complete this methodological framework, a study is considered robust when the same data yield the same conclusions despite variations in the analytical pipeline (Figure 1, bottom-left), and as generalisable when the conclusions hold across both entirely new datasets and different analytical methods (Figure 1, bottom-right) [10]. Although model reliability is related to these terms, it is not placed directly within the data–analysis matrix shown in Figure 1, because it represents a broader clinical property rather than a purely computational relationship between datasets and workflows. While the matrix verifies that a pipeline consistently recreates outputs, reliability refers to the broader clinical truth and accuracy of the underlying model. As illustrated in Figure 2, a model could theoretically be perfectly reproducible and generalisable (*i.e.*, producing tightly clustered, consistent outputs) yet remain entirely unreliable if it systematically misclassifies a physiological state (Figure 2a). Achieving true reliability ensures that the model outputs consistently align with physiological reality (Figure 2b), a critical requirement that demands thorough benchmarking against appropriate clinical reference data [7].

While the principles of computational reproducibility are important across computational sciences, their application in healthcare raises additional practical challenges. Medical data are closely associated with patient privacy, so computational reproducibility frameworks must balance the scientific need for transparent and independent verification with the ethical and legal obligation to protect sensitive health information. At the same time, the consequences of computational irreproducibility may be especially important in medical applications, where computational results can influence clinically relevant interpretations, predictions, or decisions. In applied ML for healthcare, computational reproducibility is therefore not an abstract methodological ideal, but a basic safety expectation that the same input should produce the same output when the same method is used under the same analytical conditions [14]. For example, if a model detects an arrhythmia from an ECG recording, the predicted class should not change simply because the analysis was repeated on another workstation, after a routine software update, or by a different team member executing the same pipeline [14]. In this sense, computational reproducibility helps ensure that repeated analyses give the same result when the same data and workflow are used. Differences in output should therefore not arise from undocumented changes

		Data	
		Same	Different
Analysis	Same	Reproducible	Replicable
	Different	Robust	Generalisable

Figure 1: The definitions of reproducible, replicable, robust, and generalisable research. The figure is adopted from [10] available under the CC BY 4.0 DEED license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>, accessed on 2.6.2026.)

in code, software versions, execution environment, or intermediate processing steps, but only from real changes in the data or from intentionally modified methodological choices.

Accordingly, this paper focuses on computational reproducibility in ML for applications in healthcare. Although the discussed principles are relevant to a broader range of healthcare data, ECG analysis is used throughout the overview as a concrete running example that connects the methodological discussion with a practical healthcare application. Based on the definition adopted in this manuscript, computational reproducibility relies on the precise combination of the original data, source code, and appropriate documentation. From this perspective, computational reproducibility is not determined by code alone, but by the integrity of the entire workflow. For this reason, the overview is organized around four consecutive stages of a typical ML pipeline:

- data source and accessibility,
- preprocessing and annotation,
- model development and training, and
- evaluation and validation.

To provide a consistent and systematic analysis, the same general structure is applied to each of these four stages. Specifically, each section examines why the given stage is important for computational reproducibility, what aspects are characteristic of software-based and ML workflows, where computational reproducibility may be compromised in practice, and which state-of-the-art solutions and best practices have been proposed to reduce the identified risks. Where relevant, additional constraints specific to medical applications are also highlighted. Finally, the practical implications of these issues are illustrated through their relation to a concrete healthcare study.

2 Data sources and accessibility

As shown in Table 1, all definitions of computational reproducibility emphasize that the original data must be available, accessible, and preserved in the same form as used in the original study. This means that the dataset should be complete, unchanged, clearly versioned, and traceable to the analysis that

Figure 2: Conceptual distinction between computational reproducibility and clinical reliability. (a) A model demonstrating high reproducibility and generalisability (tightly clustered outputs) but lacking reliability, as it systematically deviates from the clinical ground truth (the center of the target). (b) A clinically reliable model, where consistent computational outputs align accurately with the physiological reference data.

produced the reported results. Consequently, data sources, data availability, and data access represent the first critical stages at which computational reproducibility can be compromised.

Computational reproducibility cannot be achieved if the data used for model development are unavailable or if the conditions for access are insufficiently described, as independent researchers are then unable to verify reported results or reconstruct the analytical workflow. In contexts where data can be sufficiently anonymized, and the risk of re-identification is negligible, datasets may be released openly under clearly defined reuse terms, such as those provided by the Creative Commons license [15]. However, in healthcare applications, data sharing is subject to stricter conditions because datasets often contain sensitive health information, and privacy protection remains a primary consideration. In such settings, computational reproducibility does not necessarily require unrestricted public release; rather, it requires transparent and well-documented access procedures that allow independent verification while protecting participants' privacy. In practice, this involves formal de-identification, controlled access, Data Use Agreements (DUA), and the credentialing of users. A representative example is the PhysioNet repository [16], which distinguishes between open, restricted, and credentialed-access datasets. The example of a credentialed-access resource is the MIMIC family of datasets [16, 17, 18]. MIMIC is not a single dataset, but a set of related clinical repositories that include de-identified hospital data, intensive care data, emergency department data, and signal-based modules. One relevant example is MIMIC-IV-ECG [16, 19], which contains approximately 800,000 diagnostic electrocardiograms across nearly 160,000 unique patients, also represented in the MIMIC-IV Clinical Database. Additional derived resources, such as MIMIC-IV-ECG-Ext-ICD [16, 20, 21], link ECG recordings with clinical diagnostic labels, making them relevant for ECG-based prediction studies. These datasets are not fully public, but are provided through a governed access process that includes user credentialing and mandatory training. Thus, for medical data, the key requirement is not absolute openness, but reproducible access under conditions that are explicit, standardized, and ethically justified.

A distinct challenge emerges when ML studies are performed on previously available datasets. In this case, the central issue is not the availability of data, but whether the exact input can be identified and reconstructed. Referencing a dataset only by its common name is often insufficient, since different versions, mirrors, and locally modified releases may exist [7]. For this reason, Authors should provide the exact sources of the data, the relevant accession identifier or persistent link, the version or release

Table 1: The list of definitions of computational reproducibility with appropriate source. The definition selected for use in this study is marked in bold.

Definition	Source
“Computational reproducibility refers [...] in particular whether the same results can be obtained from the data and code used in the original study.”	[11]
“An article about computational science in a scientific publication is not the scholarship itself, it is merely advertising of the scholarship. The actual scholarship is the complete software development environment and the complete set of instructions that generated the figures.”	[12]
“Computational reproducibility is the ability to use the materials from a past study (such as data, code, and documentation) to regenerate the outputs, including figures and tables, to confirm the study’s findings.”	[7]
“A computational experiment is deemed reproducible if the same data and methods are available to replicate quantitative results by any independent researcher, anywhere and at any time, granted they have the required computing power.”	[9]
“The measurement can be obtained with stated precision by a different team using the same measurement procedure, the same measuring system, under the same operating conditions, in the same or a different location on multiple trials. For computational experiments, this means that an independent group can obtain the same result using the author’s own artefacts.”	[13]

used, the date of access, and a precise account of all cohort-construction, filtering, segmentation, annotation, and preprocessing steps that lead from the original resource to the final analysis set [15, 22]. To facilitate long-term findability and citation accuracy, Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), such as Digital Object Identifier (DOI), or handles, should be assigned not only to the final dataset but to all shared research objects, including data dictionaries and cohort-definition scripts [23]. Even when ethical or legal restrictions prevent the redistribution of raw patients’ data, computational reproducibility can still be strengthened by sharing intermediate outputs, such as cleaned recordings, derived variables, extracted features, annotation tables, and executable code for sample selection and preprocessing. A good example is the Normal Sinus Rhythm RR Interval Database on PhysioNet [16], which provides beat annotation files derived from 54 long-term ECG recordings, while the original ECG recordings are not available. In this case, researchers can repeat HRV- and RR-interval-based analyses using the shared beat-to-beat information, although the original ECG waveforms cannot be directly inspected.

Data availability alone is still not enough if the accompanying metadata are poor. The scale of this issue is significant. This challenge is further underscored by a systematic assessment of health sciences data sources in Canada, which found that 79% lacked standardized metadata, a deficiency that directly led to poor discoverability and created significant barriers for researchers attempting to reuse restricted datasets [24]. A reusable dataset must be described with enough detail to explain what the samples represent, how they were collected, which subjects or records were excluded, what the labels mean, and which transformations had already been applied before the ML workflow even started. The FAIR principles (which stand for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) place strong emphasis on rich metadata and provenance exactly because data without adequate context is difficult to

interpret, compare, or reuse reliably [25]. In practical terms, this means that Authors should provide a Data Dictionary that explicitly defines every variable, unit, and categorical label used in the analysis, ensuring that these descriptors are accessible and interpretable by both humans and machines, and report key dataset descriptors, while adapting the reported information to the specific data type [25, 26]. For ECG data, this includes the acquisition setting, recording device, lead configuration, sampling frequency, signal units, recording duration, preprocessing steps, annotation source, label definition, missing or excluded recordings, and inclusion and exclusion criteria. These descriptors make it possible to understand how the ECG signals were collected, processed, and linked to the reported labels, as shown in openly shared cardiographic datasets with accompanying documentation [27, 28]. [7, 8, 9]

The way data is stored also matters. For reproducible work, analysis-ready data should preferably be released in machine-readable, non-proprietary formats rather than only as spreadsheet files, because open formats support interoperability, long-term access, and reuse across different software environments. Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS) [29] provides an established framework for this purpose, distinguishing between “preferred” formats for long-term preservation and “non-preferred” formats that may hinder future reuse. Simple tabular data should ideally be deposited in Comma Separated Values (CSV) or OpenDocument Spreadsheet (ODS) format, rather than only in proprietary Microsoft Office Excel (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, WA, USA) spreadsheet workbooks such as .xls or .xlsx. Likewise, structured text-based information may be shared in formats such as eXtensible Markup Language (XML) or Unicode plain text, depending on the nature of the data. For time-series physiological signals, commonly used open formats include the European Data Format (EDF) [30], its extended version, European Data Format Plus (EDF+) [31], as well as Wave-Form DataBase (WFDB)-compatible record structures [16, 32]. EDF was originally developed for the exchange of digitized polygraphic sleep recordings, while EDF+ extends EDF by supporting a wider range of physiological recordings, including discontinuous recordings and time-stamped annotations [30, 31]. WFDB-compatible records are widely used in PhysioNet for storing, sharing, and analyzing physiological waveform and annotation data [16]. In WFDB-compatible records, binary signal files are coupled with header files (.hea) and, when available, annotation files (.atr), which help preserve numerical precision and metadata integrity. Similarly, in clinical imaging, the Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) standard is widely used for preserving the image matrix together with diagnostic metadata [33, 34]. Furthermore, human interventions during data curation, such as record removal or label correction, can fundamentally alter the dataset and should therefore be recorded through version-controlled logs or code, so that curation remains a traceable computational process [7, 9].

A practical example of these principles lays in PTB-XL [16, 35, 36], a publicly available ECG dataset hosted on PhysioNet [16] with a versioned DOI and open access under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>, accessed 20.4.2026). The dataset is consisted of 21799 clinical 12-lead ECG recordings, which are distributed in WFDB format as paired .dat and .hea files, with both the original 500 Hz recordings and a downsampled 100 Hz version. Record-level metadata are provided separately in *ptbxl_database.csv*, while the annotation scheme is documented in *scp_statements.csv*, which stores the corresponding SCP-ECG statements and their mappings. In this sense, PTB-XL illustrates how reproducible reuse of an existing dataset depends not only on public availability, but also on stable versioning, explicit licensing, machine-readable metadata, and predefined evaluation structure. PTB-XL can also be viewed as a larger and more ML-oriented successor to the earlier PTB Diagnostic ECG Database on PhysioNet [16, 37], which emerged from the same long-term PTB project. but contains only 549 records from a single site and provides only one label per record, whereas PTB-XL offers multi-label, machine-readable annotations across a broader range of pathologies.

3 Preprocessing and annotation

Preprocessing is one of the most common places where computational reproducibility is compromised, because papers often describe it only briefly even though small technical choices can change the final ML result [38, 39, 40]. In terms of biomedical signals, the slight changes in filter types, cutoff frequencies, padding rules, resampling strategies, or window definitions can produce different training inputs from the same raw data [41, 42]. A practical way to reduce this problem is to treat preprocessing as a reproducible part of the pipeline rather than as background routine. In practice, this means reporting the exact order of steps, all parameter values, software packages and versions, and preferably releasing the preprocessing scripts or workflow itself, so that another group can regenerate the same analysis-ready data instead of trying to reconstruct them from a short textual description. [9]

Annotation and manual curation create a second major source of variability, especially in healthcare-based ML, where labels often depend on expert judgment. Data labeling, referred to as annotation within medicine, is the systematic process of assigning descriptive categories or numerical values to raw data points. This procedure involves the application of a predefined schema by human experts to transform qualitative or physiological observations into structured inputs suitable for algorithmic training [43]. Consequently, the reliability of an ML model is inherently dependent on the consistency of this human-mediated translation of raw data into discrete labels. Studies in medical ML have shown that even experienced annotators can disagree, and that inconsistent labeling instructions or poorly documented manual corrections can directly affect model training and evaluation [44, 45]. For that reason, reproducible studies should describe not only the final labels but also how they were created: who annotated the data (in term of expertise), including the specific clinical background and years of experience of the annotators, for example board-certified cardiologists versus medical students, what instructions they followed, whether multiple annotators were used, how disagreements were resolved, which samples were manually corrected or excluded, and whether uncertain cases were kept, relabeled, or removed. This is particularly important in ECG analysis, where the reliability of ground-truth labels is highly dependent on the level of expert judgment. Recent reporting frameworks argue that annotation collection itself should be documented in a reproducible way, with explicit protocols and metadata, so that manual decisions become traceable rather than hidden. In ECG studies, this also includes interactive annotation software that displays the signal, allows the annotator to mark beat locations or waveform landmarks, and stores these decisions as structured annotation files. For example, PhysioNet tools, such as WAVE and LightWAVE, support the visualization and editing of ECG waveforms and associated annotations, including beat-level and waveform-level markers [16, 32, 46]. Therefore, the annotation software, its version, annotation rules, exported file format, manual correction steps, and annotator roles should be reported as part of the reproducible workflow. [7, 47]

A practical example is the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database (MBAD) [16, 48], which is a widely used ECG dataset created to test how well algorithms detect and classify arrhythmias, and unlike many ECG datasets, it includes expert annotations for each heartbeat, not just for the recording as a whole. In MBAD, two or more cardiologists independently annotated each record, and disagreements were subsequently resolved to produce the released reference annotations for each beat. This is important, because it shows that computational reproducibility in ECG ML depends not only on access to waveform recordings, but also on access to a clearly documented annotation protocol. In contrast, many modern ECG classification datasets, such as PTB-XL, assign one or more diagnostic statements to the recording as a whole rather than providing beat-by-beat labels. Thus, the computational reproducibility requirements differ depending on the annotation granularity: for beat-level tasks, researchers must preserve detailed annotation rules and beat annotations, whereas for recording-level classification tasks, they must preserve the labeling schema used for each full record.

4 Model development and training

Model development and training are the stage at which general software-engineering practices meet ML-specific requirements for computational reproducibility. A persistent challenge is the reliance on “local” implementations – *ad-hoc* collections of scripts containing hidden helper functions, complex dependencies, or undocumented manual adjustments – which often prevent the reconstruction of the reported model, even when the underlying data are available. To mitigate this, implementations should prioritize Free/Libre and Open Source Software (FLOSS) such as Python [49] or R [50], which ensure the transparency required for computational verification. In particular, Python supports a mature ecosystem of libraries (*e.g.*, PyTorch [51], TensorFlow [52], or Scikit-learn [53]) optimized for complex ML workflows [15]. Furthermore, these implementations should be released under recognized open licenses, such as the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) license or the GNU General Public License (GPL), to ensure they are both inspectable and legally reusable. [7, 9]

However, in ML research, the source code alone is often insufficient for full computational reproducibility, because it represents only the instructions for the training process, not the final state of the system. To ensure an experiment can be faithfully reconstructed or applied to new data, researchers must also preserve the trained model artefacts, which encompass specific numerical weights (the parameters learned during training) and the architectural configurations that define the model structure. Furthermore, independent re-execution of the training process is not always possible due to practical constraints, such as the lack of specialized high-performance hardware or the unavailability of the original training datasets. In such instances, the preservation of the trained model is the only way to enable downstream analysis and verification. Consequently, specialized model hubs such as Hugging Face [54] serve as essential infrastructures for the standardized sharing and versioning of these large-scale artefacts, ensuring that the research remains accessible and functional even when the original training environment cannot be replicated. [7, 9, 15, 22]

An example of this is the study by Ribeiro *et al.*, [4], which developed a neural network for automatic diagnosis of abnormalities in standard 12-lead ECG recordings. From a computational reproducibility perspective, this study is particularly important because the Ribeiro *et al.*, [4] released the companion source code publicly, as well as deposited pre-trained model weights openly through Zenodo, thereby allowing other researchers to inspect the implementation and rerun inference without repeating the full original training procedure [4]. At the same time, the full underlying training dataset was not openly available, but access could be requested for non-commercial research under appropriate data-use agreements. This example shows that, even when the full training dataset is available only under controlled access conditions, computational reproducibility can still be strengthened by sharing executable code, an open test set, and preserved model artefacts [4].

Given that the model training process typically requires an iterative search across diverse experimental settings and hyperparameter configurations, the adoption of version control systems like Git is essential. Git ensures comprehensive traceability by systematically recording every modification, alongside metadata specifying the Author and the rationale for the change via commit messages. Furthermore, it facilitates robust team collaboration by allowing researchers to develop and test new features on isolated branches before merging validated updates into the main codebase. In addition to Git-based version control, the adoption of Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELNs) offers a technical solution for documenting the iterative nature of model development, enabling the systematic recording of experimental settings and the rigorous definition of workflows for generating clinical insights [55]. However, while platforms such as GitHub have become the standard for hosting and sharing code, they are not designed for long-term academic preservation and do not issue DOIs. Therefore, to provide a stable, citable record of the exact software state used at the time of publication, researchers should archive their repositories externally by linking a specific GitHub release to a persistent repository like Zenodo to generate a permanent DOI. [7, 9, 15, 22]

Even when source code is openly shared, computational reproducibility may still fail if the computational environment is incompletely specified. In ML, an identical script can produce divergent results or fail to execute entirely due to undocumented differences in hardware configurations, operating systems, or software versions. For instance, the code may be processed by the Central Processing Unit (CPU), which serves as the primary processor of the computer. Alternatively, workloads are frequently offloaded to a Graphics Processing Unit (GPU), which enables parallelizing computations suitable to accelerate ML training process. To fully utilize GPU units, specific software platforms are required to bridge the ML frameworks with the hardware. NVIDIA systems utilize the Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA), which allows frameworks like PyTorch and TensorFlow to interface directly with the hardware. Similarly, Apple devices rely on Metal Performance Shaders (MPS) as the backend for executing ML tasks on their specific architectures. This hardware dependence is critical, since frameworks rely on distinct low-level routines, drivers, and numerical implementations depending on the active device and software stack. Consequently, even a minor alteration in a framework version, driver configuration, or hardware backend can fundamentally alter execution behavior, memory allocation, runtime, and the final numerical output itself. For this reason, hardware reporting should go beyond naming the CPU or GPU and should also include numerical and memory-related settings that affect execution. The specific floating-point precision used during both training and inference (*e.g.*, float32 or float64) should also be reported, as lower-precision computations can introduce numerical drift that affects model convergence and final accuracy. For this reason, documenting the maximum Random Access Memory (RAM) and Video RAM (VRAM) usage required for training and inference is essential for computational reproducibility, as it informs independent researchers whether the pipeline can be executed on standard consumer hardware or requires specialized high-performance clusters [7, 22]. [56]

A further source of computational irreproducibility arises from differences in the Operating System (OS). Even when the same code and the same data are used, execution may still vary across Windows, Linux, and macOS because these systems differ in file paths, shell behavior, available system libraries, and other platform-specific settings. For this reason, reproducible studies should describe the OS explicitly and, when needed, provide the analysis in an encapsulated form. One option is a virtual machine, which emulate an entirely separate computer complete with its own full operating system. This provides strong isolation, but virtual machines are relatively large and resource-intensive. In practice, containers are often the more convenient solution. A container is a lightweight software unit that packages an application together with its runtime, libraries, and configuration files. Unlike a full virtual machine, it relies on the existing operating system of the host computer to manage hardware resources, which makes it more lightweight and easier to reproduce across different computing environments. Docker has become the most widely used standard for this purpose, because it allows the same container image to be built, shared, and executed across different computing environments with far fewer hidden system differences. Although containers do not remove every source of variation, especially when low-level kernel behavior or specialized hardware is involved, they greatly reduce operating-system-related discrepancies and are therefore the preferred practical standard for most ML workflows. [7, 9, 56, 57]

At a more local level, computational reproducibility also depends on documenting the project-specific software environment. In Python, a virtual environment isolates the packages used in different projects, thereby reducing dependency conflicts. This is especially important when the program is to be executed on another computer, because the environment specification allows the required libraries used on the original computer to be installed automatically in the new one. The simplest reproducible record is a *requirements.txt* file, which lists the Python packages to be installed, together with pinned versions. In practice, such a file can be generated from an existing environment and then reused to recreate the same package set on another machine. Conda environments serve a similar purpose, plus they can also manage Python itself and non-Python packages. Their usual exchange format is a *environment.yml*

```

name: reproducible_ml_env
channels:
  - pytorch
  - conda-forge
  - defaults
dependencies:
  - python=3.10.12
  - pip=23.2.1
  - numpy=1.25.2
  - pandas=2.0.3
  - scikit-learn=1.3.0
  - pytorch=2.0.1
  - pip:
    - wfdb==4.1.2
    - neurokit2==0.2.5

```

Figure 3: Illustrative example of an *environment.yml* file for recreating the software environment of a reproducible machine learning study. It records the environment name, package sources, Python version, and required dependencies, including both Conda and pip packages.

file, which can record the environment name, package channels, Python version, and package dependencies. An example of such an *environment.yml* file is shown in Figure 3. This file defines the exact software environment used in the study, including Python version, the package sources (“channels”), and the main libraries with their versions, so that the same environment can be recreated on another computer with minimal ambiguity. Therefore, a reproducible ML study should ideally provide both the environment specification file and the instructions needed to rebuild it. For complex workflows this environment should additionally be wrapped in a Docker image. [9, 56, 57]

However, containerized code alone does not account for the inherent stochasticity of ML workflows. Model training depends on several pseudorandom processes, including model weight initialization, data shuffling, mini-batch formation, dropout, and, in some studies, hyperparameter search [7, 9, 15]. To establish experimental control over these sources of variance, Authors must explicitly fix and report the initialization seed values utilized by the core programming language (*e.g.*, Python), numerical libraries (*e.g.*, NumPy, random), and the specific ML frameworks (*e.g.*, Scikit-learn, TensorFlow, or PyTorch). Furthermore, studies should document whether deterministic execution algorithms were explicitly mandated at the backend level. At the same time, not all variability can be fully controlled, because different libraries, devices, and backend implementations may still introduce small differences in the computations. For this reason, reproducible studies should clearly report both the pseudorandom settings that were fixed and the remaining sources of variability that may still affect the results.

Beyond the initialization of model parameters, the broader methodological framework used to tune the model must also be transparently documented. Ambiguous statements such as “hyperparameters were optimized” are insufficient for computational reconstruction and must be replaced with explicit operational details [58]. To ensure full computational reproducibility, researchers must rigorously define the hyperparameter search space, the specific selection algorithm utilized (*e.g.*, grid search, random search, or Bayesian optimization), and the precise evaluation protocol applied (*e.g.*, 5-fold cross-validation or a fixed validation holdout set). Although the strict word limits imposed by scientific journals frequently preclude exhaustive methodological descriptions within the primary manuscript, such constraints must not compromise the integrity of the research. The established best practice dictates that these granular algorithmic details be thoroughly detailed in supplementary materials or, preferably, preserved as explicit configuration files within the archived codebase on persistent repositories. A practical example is provided by the supplementary material of the CardioPRINT study [27,

28], where the hyperparameter-tuning procedure is documented by reporting the predefined search ranges, the evaluation strategy based on cross-validation, the tuning method used to compare candidate settings, the final selected hyperparameter values, and a short discussion of what these values may indicate about the data and the classification task. Instead of reporting only the best performance of each model, the Supplementary materials make the tuning process traceable by showing which modelling choices were tested and how the final configuration was selected [27, 28]. This type of documentation is useful because it helps readers distinguish between the clinical or physiological meaning of the data and the technical choices that shape the final ML performance. [22]

In healthcare ML, computational reproducibility should also be linked with interpretability and explainability, because a model that can be rerun is not necessarily understandable or clinically useful. In this context, interpretability refers to the possibility of interpreting the results of the model, while explainability refers to the possibility of explaining the operating principles of the whole analytical procedure. Researchers should therefore report not only the final performance metrics, but also the information needed to understand how the model reaches its outputs, including the input variables, selected features, feature-importance procedures, and explanation methods. This is particularly important for ECG-based ML, where clinically meaningful signal characteristics, such as waveform morphology, intervals, amplitudes, or rhythm-related features, can help connect model behavior with physiological interpretation. In this sense, reproducibility supports the technical verification of the result, while interpretability supports the scientific and clinical understanding of that result. Together, they can help physicians more easily connect the model output with familiar clinical reasoning, bridge the gap between computational results and medical decision-making, and develop greater trust in the system when its behavior is transparent and clinically meaningful. [59, 60, 61]

A practical summary of the main requirements for computational reproducibility during ML model training is shown in Figure 4. The figure organizes the training stage into several key questions that researchers should answer before publication, including whether the implementation is open, whether the trained model artefacts are preserved, whether the computational environment can be recreated, and whether model tuning and interpretation are transparently reported. In this way, the figure emphasizes that reproducible ML training is not ensured by source code alone, but by the combined documentation and sharing of code, model artefacts, software environment, random settings, tuning protocol, and clinically meaningful interpretation. To provide a clear roadmap for researchers, these requirements can be further operationalized using the tiered reproducibility standards proposed by Heil *et al.* [22]. Under this framework, achieving basic essential computational reproducibility corresponds to the Bronze standard, which requires that the data, source code, and trained model artefacts are made available whenever ethically and legally possible, or that data access restrictions and access procedures are explicitly documented. Moving beyond these basic requirements into recommended best practices, the Silver standard demands that key analysis details are meticulously recorded, random components are set to deterministic execution, and environment dependencies can be set up using a single command (*e.g.*, via a pinned Conda `environment.yml` file or configuration files). Finally, the highest tier of reproducibility is the Gold standard, which is reached when the entire analysis workflow is encapsulated and reproducible with a single command. It is an ideal objective that is best facilitated by wrapping the complete pipeline inside containerized software units such as Docker. Categorizing these methodologies ensures that researchers can systematically evaluate and elevate the reproducible properties of their machine learning pipelines. [22]

5 Evaluation and validation

Model evaluation is the last step in the ML workflow, where a method often appears stronger than it really is, especially when the test procedure is not fully separated from model development. The most common problem is data leakage: the model is evaluated on data that are not truly independent,

Figure 4: Practical checklist for supporting computational reproducibility during machine learning (ML) model training. FLOSS – Free/Libre and Open Source Software; MIT – Massachusetts Institute of Technology license; GPL – GNU General Public License; DOI – Digital Object Identifier; OS – Operating System; CPU – Central Processing Unit; GPU – Graphics Processing Unit; CV – Cross-Validation

because some kind of overlap exists between splits, preprocessing is performed before splitting, or test data influence feature selection and tuning [62]. Leakage can produce strongly inflated results and has been documented across many scientific fields using ML. A practical solution is to define the evaluation split first, keep the test set untouched until the very end, and perform all data-dependent operations, including normalization, imputation, feature selection, and hyperparameter tuning, using only the training data within each fold. In healthcare, the separation of training and test data should reflect the intended real-world use of the model. For example, if several samples are extracted using data from the same patient, all of them should usually be kept in only one subset, because otherwise the model may partly “recognize” the same person during testing instead of truly generalizing to a new patient. Likewise, data from one hospital may need to be kept separate when cross-site generalization is being assessed, and later time periods should be reserved for testing when the goal is to predict future cases, rather than splitting individual samples at random. An example of appropriate evaluation design is demonstrated by Lima *et al.* [63] in their development of a DL model for ECG-based cardiovascular age prediction. To ensure the generalizability of their results, Lima *et al.* [63] evaluated their model not only on an internal hold-out (*i.e.*, test) subset of the primary development data (the CODE cohort), but also across two independent, external datasets. The external evaluation showed that the model retained prognostic value across datasets: patients with an ECG-age more than 8 years higher than their chronological age had increased mortality risk in the internal CODE-15% test cohort, as well as in the external ELSA-Brasil and SaMi-Trop cohorts. However, the prediction accuracy for chronological age was lower in the external cohorts, with reported Mean Absolute Error (MAE) values of 8.38 years in CODE-15%, 8.44 years in ELSA-Brasil, and 10.04 years in SaMi-Trop, showing both the value and the limits of cross-dataset generalization [63]. By testing the algorithm on entirely distinct patient populations rather than merely resampling the original data, this approach rigorously assesses if the model maintains its predictive reliability when deployed in new clinical environments, ensuring the system has learned true physiological markers rather than the inherited biases of the training cohort.

A second problem is the use of incomplete or overly favorable performance measures. In medical ML, results are still often summarized by a single number, such as accuracy or Area Under the Receiver Operating characteristic Curve (AUC-ROC), even though these metrics alone do not show whether the predicted probabilities are clinically reliable. The guidelines on evaluating clinical prediction models emphasize that discrimination and calibration should be assessed together, and that no single calibration summary is sufficient on its own [47]. A model may separate cases from controls reasonably well and still systematically overestimate or underestimate risk. This distinction is particularly important in healthcare applications, where calibration is often as critical as discrimination, as a model can correctly identify a high-risk patient but substantially overestimates the absolute risk [26], which may still lead to inappropriate clinical interventions or unnecessary patient anxiety. In practice, this means that evaluation should report multiple evaluation metrics (*e.g.*, Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1 score, AUC-ROC) and a set of calibration assessments (*e.g.*, Brier score), ideally including a calibration plot [47].

A third problem is the assumption that strong internal validation automatically implies real-world usefulness. Cross-validation and hold-out testing within the same cohort are useful, but they do not show whether the model will work in a new hospital, on a new device, in another time period, or in a population with different case mix. This is one of the main reasons why models that look promising during development often disappoint in later use. A recent systematic review of Intensive Care Unit (ICU) prediction models found that external validation was still uncommon, and that performance was generally lower when models were tested on external data than in the original development studies [64]. The practical solution is to include external validation whenever possible, as shown in the study by Lima *et al.*, [63], preferably using data from another institution, a different period, or another cohort collected under different conditions [65]. When such data are not available, Authors should state this limitation clearly and avoid presenting internal validation as proof of general usefulness.

Meaningful model evaluation also requires benchmark datasets or benchmark evaluation protocols with predefined data splits and performance metrics, so that newly proposed models can be compared under the same conditions. In simple terms, this means that different methods should be tested on the same task, using the same rules, rather than each study defining its own evaluation setup. Otherwise, reported improvements may reflect differences in the test setting rather than genuine superiority of the model itself. Within such a benchmark framework, newly proposed ML models should be evaluated against appropriate reference methods, including standard clinical scores or simple linear models, to ensure that increased computational complexity is justified by a statistically significant improvement in clinical performance [8, 47]. A prominent realization of this principle in cardiographic research is the PTB-XL dataset, which provides explicitly recommended training-test splits and rich, standardized annotations designed specifically to facilitate the objective comparability of ML algorithms. By using this dataset structure, Strothoff *et al.* [66] performed a benchmark study in the sense that several ECG-analysis models were evaluated on the same dataset, under shared experimental rules, and across predefined tasks such as ECG statement prediction, age and sex prediction, and signal-quality assessment. Therefore, the value of the study is not only that it reports strong model performance, but that it provides reference results against which later ECG models can be compared more objectively.

The model evaluation also becomes weak when only the most favorable result is reported. In practical terms, this means reporting Confidence Intervals (CI) or comparable uncertainty measures, repeating training and evaluation when stochastic variation is expected, and stating clearly whether the reported value comes from one split, repeated cross-validation, bootstrap resampling, or an external test set. For clinical prediction models, recent reporting guidance also recommends a transparent description of all validation procedures and performance measures, so that readers can judge whether high reported performance reflects a rigorous evaluation design rather than an overly optimistic or poorly controlled testing procedure. [26, 47]

Finally, when true external validation is not feasible, for example, due to strict privacy regulations, the absence of comparable cohorts, or the rarity of a specific pathology, this limitation should be stated explicitly rather than replaced by ordinary random internal splitting. In such cases, researchers can only strengthen internal evidence and assess whether the model behaves robustly under clinically plausible sources of variation. For ECG analysis, one practical option is semi-synthetic stress testing, where controlled levels of baseline wander, muscle artifact, electrode-motion noise, amplitude changes, missing leads, or lead-reversal simulations are introduced into the internal test set. This principle is illustrated by the MIT-BIH Noise Stress Test Database [16, 67], in which clean ECG recordings are combined with calibrated noise segments while retaining known reference annotations. In addition to such technical stress testing, researchers may construct an expert-curated challenge set from the available data, including clear normal cases, clear pathological cases, borderline examples, low-quality recordings, and clinically important failure modes. This set should be locked before evaluation and reviewed by domain experts to assess whether model outputs, errors, and explanations are physiologically plausible and consistent with diagnostic expectations [68, 69]. Such expert-guided evaluation is not a replacement for independent external validation, but it can identify clinically implausible behavior that standard aggregate metrics may hide [68, 69].

6 Discussion

Beyond individual projects, the scientific method relies on published results serving as a reliable “ground truth” upon which subsequent theories, algorithms, and clinical applications can be built. However, when independent investigators cannot verify prior findings, this cumulative process collapses, leaving researchers to build upon irreproducible artefacts and unreliable reports. In a survey reported by Nature [70], it is indicated that 70% of researchers said they had attempted and failed to reproduce others’ experiments, and over half reported failing to reproduce their own. However, the

reason for the computational reproducibility crisis, 60% of researchers indicate that it is pressure to publish and selective reporting. This matters for ML in healthcare, because model development is inherently iterative, and future studies often reuse earlier preprocessing choices, labels, splits, and architectures as defaults, which becomes risky when those defaults are not verifiable. In the longer term, independent confirmation is one of the core ways research communities build confidence that findings reflect something real rather than a fragile byproduct of a particular analytic setup [14]. Improving the reliability of published outcomes, therefore, requires a coordinated effort in which peer reviewers are empowered to identify missing documentation, and scientific journals adopt reporting guidelines that are as rigorous for computational methods as they are for experimental data [7]. For this reason, Table 2 summarizes the main challenges across the ML workflow and the practical steps that can reduce these risks.

Computational irreproducibility is also an efficiency problem because it can turn research effort into results that cannot be audited, reused, or reliably extended. For example, preclinical research, conducted by Freedman *et al.*, [71], estimated that the cumulative prevalence of irreproducible preclinical research exceeds 50%, corresponding to roughly US\$28 billion per year spent on preclinical research that is not reproducible in the United States alone. This means that whenever methods or a pipeline are not reproducible, other teams must spend time and funding re-deriving basic implementation details instead of continuing on already established ground. In medical ML specifically, these costs are amplified because datasets are often available only under controlled access conditions, while important labels or outcomes may require lengthy expert review or prolonged clinical follow-up. As a result, repeating cohort construction or relabeling is expensive, slow, and in some cases impossible without access to the original data, annotation rules, clinical expertise, and software tools used in the study.

Although this manuscript uses ECG analysis to illustrate general challenges in computational reproducibility, the underlying framework is broadly applicable to other healthcare data modalities. However, when these principles are transferred to other medical domains, researchers must address concrete, data-specific sources of computational irreproducibility. For example, in medical imaging, the computational reproducibility bottleneck extends beyond model architecture and includes scanner protocols, image reconstruction, segmentation, annotation instructions, and feature extraction. This is illustrated by standardization initiatives in image-biomarker research [72], as well as by evidence that differences in annotation instructions can substantially affect the results in the analysis of medical images [45]. In wearable-device and digital-biomarker research, the critical reproducible steps may occur even further upstream, because the final model input can be shaped by sensor type, sampling frequency, filtering, compression, firmware, and proprietary algorithms used by the device. Therefore, the hardware, firmware, software, and data-processing pipeline should be documented together with the analytical code [73]. For models trained on electronic health records (EHRs), the main computational reproducibility challenges shift toward data governance, cohort construction, and curation, including database versioning, missing-data handling, encodings/mappings, and the transformations used to convert routine clinical records into structured, analysis-ready variables [17, 47]. Ultimately, regardless of whether the input consists of physiological signals, medical images, wearable-sensor measurements, or EHR-derived variables, the core requirement remains the same: computational reproducibility requires a traceable data source, explicit preprocessing and annotation rules, version-controlled code and execution environments, preserved model artefacts, and evaluation protocols that permit independent verification under clearly defined conditions [22].

While definitions differ in terminology (as summarized in Table 1), most frameworks effectively reduce computational reproducibility to a small set of concrete requirements: access to the data, access to the executable analysis code, and sufficient documentation to rerun the full workflow under defined conditions [7, 9, 22]. To make these requirements easier to apply in practice, Table 2 presents a checklist-style overview of common challenges and corresponding practical solutions across the ML workflow, while also indicating the main responsibility or oversight role associated with each

Table 2: Practical solutions for identified issues in machine learning pipelines. Resp. – Responsibility; A – Authors/Researchers responsible for implementation and reporting; R – Reviewer(s) responsible for methodological and reporting assessment; E – Journal Editors/journals responsible for defining and enforcing requirements through Guide for Authors, reporting guidelines, and open-science policies.

Step	Identified Issue	Practical Solution	Resp.
Data source and accessibility	Data unavailable or access conditions unclear	Provide explicit access procedures	A, R, E
	Dataset source/version not fully identifiable	Report exact source, version, accession/persistent link, and date of access	A, R, E
	Poor metadata	Include rich metadata/data dictionary	A, R, E
	Unsuitable storage formats	Use machine-readable preferred open formats and domain standards	A, E
	Non-comparable data storage	Establish standardized, machine-readable formats and metadata protocols for long-term storage	A, E
	Undocumented manual curation	Record all curation steps in version-controlled logs or code; share intermediate outputs when raw data cannot be released	A, R
Preprocessing and annotation	Small preprocessing choices change the final input	Treat preprocessing as part of the reproducible pipeline	A, R
	Preprocessing described too briefly	Report step order, parameters, software, and versions; release preprocessing scripts/workflows; provide detailed protocols in supplementary materials	A, R, E
	Labels depend on expert judgment	Document annotator roles, annotation instructions, annotation software/version, and any manual correction rules	A, R, E
	Annotator disagreement and undocumented corrections	Document how disagreements were resolved and how uncertain/corrected samples were handled	A, R
Model development and training	Local undocumented code; poor version traceability	Use FLOSS tools, open licenses, and Git; archive release versions with a persistent DOI	A, R, E
	Source code shared without trained artefacts	Share trained model weights and configurations (<i>e.g.</i> , HuggingFace)	A, R, E
	Incomplete environment description; OS/hardware/software differences	Provide environment files and containerized execution (<i>e.g.</i> , Docker); report hardware/OS stack	A, R, E
	Uncontrolled pseudorandomness	Fix and report seeds, deterministic settings, and uncontrolled sources of variability	A, R
	Vague hyperparameter tuning	Document search space, tuning method, and evaluation protocol explicitly	A, R
Evaluation and validation	Data leakage	Define splits first and keep the test set untouched; perform all data-dependent steps only on training data	A, R
	Overreliance on single favorable metrics; only best result reported	Report multiple metrics, calibration, and uncertainty; do not only report accuracy/AUC	A, R, E
	Internal validation presented as proof of general usefulness	Include external validation when possible; use patient/site/time-aware separation	A, R, E
	Non-comparable evaluation setups	Use benchmark datasets/protocols with predefined splits and metrics	A, R, E
	Vague validation procedures	Clearly describe all validation procedures	A, R, E
	Incomplete reporting in publications	Journals should mandate adherence to reporting guidelines, and reviewers should verify data and documentation completeness	A, R, E

recommendation. In this context, authors/researchers are primarily responsible for implementing and reporting reproducible practices, reviewers for assessing whether the reported information is sufficient for critical evaluation, and journal editors or journals for defining and enforcing appropriate reporting and open-science expectations through Guide for Authors documents, data and code availability policies, supplementary-material requirements, and editorial procedures. This initiative in the ML field is now visible in how leading ML venues operationalize computational reproducibility through reporting expectations, such as the Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS) paper checklist, which explicitly prompts Authors to provide access to data and code (or explain restrictions) and to report enough experimental detail to reproduce main results [74]. In clinical prediction modeling, the same principle appears as domain-specific reporting guidance, such as MINimum Information for Medical AI Reporting (MINIMAR) [75], the practical checklist proposed by Cabitza and Campagner [47], or the TRIPOD family of guidelines. Specifically, TRIPOD+AI 2024 guideline [26] provides updated, harmonized guidance for reporting prediction model studies that use regression or ML-based methods [76]. These frameworks therefore have complementary roles rather than being interchangeable. The NeurIPS checklist is primarily a general (domain-agnostic) ML reporting instrument focused on experimental transparency, availability of code and data, and reproducibility of computational results. MINIMAR, on the other hand, offers a concise minimum-information structure for reporting clinical AI studies, with emphasis on the clinical problem, data source, model development, performance, and intended use [75]. TRIPOD+AI 2024, however, is a more recent framework that focuses on prediction models in general (which include AI), developed as an update of the original TRIPOD framework for studies that use regression or ML-based prediction models [26]. Importantly, MINIMAR and TRIPOD+AI should not be viewed as disconnected initiatives, since the AI-specific content of TRIPOD+AI was informed by several previous reporting frameworks, including MINIMAR [26]. In practical terms, MINIMAR can be understood as a compact general reporting framework for clinical AI, while TRIPOD+AI provides a more detailed structure for reporting prediction-model development, validation, performance, and information needed to judge bias, applicability, and reproducibility [77]. In contrast, the Cabitza and Campagner checklist translates recommendations from existing medical-AI and prediction-model guidance, including MINIMAR and TRIPOD-related principles, into an explicit appraisal checklist that can be used by authors, reviewers, and editors to assess whether a medical-AI study reports enough information to support critical evaluation, reproducibility assessment, and potential reuse [47]. Importantly, the Cabitza and Campagner checklist has also been translated into Serbian [78], which may facilitate its use in local teaching, critical appraisal, and more standardized evaluation of medical AI studies. Ultimately, in ML for application in healthcare, reproducibility is not a supplementary obligation or additional step; it is an example of good scientific and clinical practice with systematic formalization of data, code, and methodological decisions that ensure reported performance metrics are both interpretable and independently verifiable. This implementation of computational reproducibility is a continuous process throughout the project rather than being added after results are obtained, which is why the emphasis is placed on training and education as core infrastructure for improving computational reproducibility [7, 9].

There is also increasing institutional interest in rewarding reproducible practice rather than treating it as invisible labor [79]. For reproducibility to become a systemic part of Open Science, however, it should gradually transition from an optional effort to a formal academic credential that is considered in researcher performance evaluations. This also requires software and curated data to be recognized as first-class research outputs with their own citable metrics, so that institutions can value the technical labor required to make a study truly reproducible. For example, the Center for Open Science describes Open Science Badges as signals that data/materials are available in a persistent location, and notes that over 100 journals offer such badges [79]. Empirically, badge adoption has been associated with large increases in reported open data in at least some journal contexts, suggesting that lightweight incentives can shift behavior. In computing, the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM) has formalized artefact review and badging terminology to encourage independent audit of

code, data, and other artefacts, and it also supports community-building through the ACM Emerging Interest Group on Reproducibility and Replicability [13]. At the broader research-culture level, national reproducibility initiatives have expanded through networks such as the UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN)² and related national initiatives, including the Serbian Reproducibility Network (RS-RN)³. These initiatives aim to foster the adoption of open and reproducible research practices by connecting researchers and institutions, providing training, promoting transparent workflows, and supporting community-building. In this context, the systematic workflow presented in this paper will be integrated into the upcoming training programs and webinars of the RS-RN, providing a localized educational framework for improving the computational integrity of medical AI research in Serbia.

Finally, the effective implementation of the steps presented in this article is not merely a matter of intent, as it demands significant, ongoing technical training. Adopting tools often championed as industry standards, such as Docker for containerized execution or Git for advanced version control, presents a steep learning curve that extends far beyond the foundational statistical and programming knowledge traditionally taught in academia [15]. Furthermore, since ML methodologies and their corresponding computational reproducibility frameworks evolve at a pace that frequently outstrips formal university curricula, researchers cannot rely solely on institutional instruction. Instead, maintaining computational reproducibility in modern ML requires continuous technical training, since software tools, repository structures, and community recommendations evolve rapidly [80]. At the same time, the current difficulties in reusing published models can be attributed largely to the absence of community-wide standards and supporting long-term infrastructure for data storage. The scientific community must therefore prioritize the establishment of standardized, machine-readable formats and metadata protocols to fully leverage the power of research data for future diagnostic and clinical applications.

7 Conclusion

Computational reproducibility in ML for healthcare applications should be viewed as a basic condition of trustworthy research, not as an optional technical addition at the end of a study. A model cannot be considered reliable if its results depend on hidden choices in data selection, undocumented preprocessing, untracked code changes, unstable software environments, or weak evaluation design. The main practical message of this paper is simple. Computational reproducibility should be treated as an integral part of every stage of the ML workflow, from data access and preprocessing to model training, evaluation, interpretation, and reporting. This includes accessible and well-described data, rich metadata, traceable curation, clearly specified preprocessing and annotation, open and version-controlled code, explicit dependencies, portable environments, shared model artefacts, and rigorous evaluation without leakage. External validation should also be performed whenever possible. In this sense, computational reproducibility is not a separate step in the workflow, rather the result of good research practice applied consistently across the entire pipeline. For ML researchers, especially in fast-moving fields, such as healthcare, this also means that technical competence must go beyond model development alone. It should include continual learning of tools, standards, and habits that make results transparent, verifiable, and reusable. Only under such conditions can ML findings move beyond high reported performance and become reliable, independently verifiable, and useful for cumulative science and practical biomedical and clinical applications.

Generative AI disclosure statement

During the preparation of this work, the first Author used GPT-5 (ChatGPT) to improve readability and language. After using this tool/service, the first Author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication. No AI-generated or AI-altered images

²<https://www.ukrn.org/>

³<https://reproducibility.rs/index.php/en>

were used. All figures were created by the Authors.

Funding

Nadica Miljković acknowledges the support from the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia [Grant No. 451-03-34/2026-03/200103]. Matija Zlatar acknowledges the support from the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia [Grant No. 451-03-33/2026-03/200026]

References

1. Dalky A, Altawalbih M, Alshani F, Khasawneh RA, Tawalbeh R, Al-Dekah AM, Alrawashdeh A, Quran TO, and ALBashtawy M. Global research trends, hotspots, impacts, and emergence of artificial intelligence and machine learning in health and medicine: a 25-year bibliometric analysis. *Healthcare*. Vol. 13. 8. MDPI. 2025 :892. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare13080892>
2. Topol EJ. High-performance medicine: the convergence of human and artificial intelligence. *Nature medicine* 2019; 25:44–56. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-018-0300-7>
3. Hannun AY, Rajpurkar P, Haghpanahi M, Tison GH, Bourn C, Turakhia MP, and Ng AY. Cardiologist-level arrhythmia detection and classification in ambulatory electrocardiograms using a deep neural network. *Nature medicine* 2019; 25:65–9. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-018-0268-3>
4. Ribeiro AH, Ribeiro MH, Paixão GM, Oliveira DM, Gomes PR, Canazart JA, Ferreira MP, Andersson CR, Macfarlane PW, Meira Jr W, et al. Automatic diagnosis of the 12-lead ECG using a deep neural network. *Nature communications* 2020; 11:1760. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-15432-4>
5. Goodfellow I, Bengio Y, and Courville A. *Deep Learning*. <http://www.deeplearningbook.org>. MIT Press, 2016
6. Meltzer D and Luengo D. Ecg-based biometric recognition: A survey of methods and databases. *Sensors* 2025; 25:1864. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s25061864>
7. Ziemann M, Poulain P, and Bora A. The five pillars of computational reproducibility: bioinformatics and beyond. *Briefings in Bioinformatics* 2023; 24. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbad375>
8. Ciobanu-Carus O, Aicher A, Kernbach JM, Regli L, Serra C, and Staartjes VE. A critical moment in machine learning in medicine: on reproducible and interpretable learning. *Acta neurochirurgica* 2024; 166:14. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00701-024-05892-8>
9. Shenouda J and Bajwa WU. A guide to computational reproducibility in signal processing and machine learning [tips & tricks]. *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine* 2023; 40:141–51. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MSP.2022.3217659>
10. Community TTW. *The Turing Way: A handbook for reproducible, ethical and collaborative research*. Version 1.2.3. 2025. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15213042>
11. Stodden V. Reproducing statistical results. *Annual Review of Statistics and Its Application* 2015; 2:1–19. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-statistics-010814-020127>
12. Buckheit JB and Donoho DL. Wavelab and reproducible research. *Wavelets and statistics*. Springer, 1995 :55–81. doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4612-2544-7_5
13. Association for Computing Machinery. *Artifact Review and Badging Current Policy*. 2026. Available from: <https://www.acm.org/publications/policies/artifact-review-and-badging-current> [Accessed on: 2026 Apr 21]

14. Sciences NA of, Medicine, Policy, Affairs G, Research Data B on, Information, Engineering D on, Sciences P, Applied C on, Statistics T, et al. Reproducibility and replicability in science. National Academies Press, 2019. doi: <https://doi.org/10.17226/25303>
15. Wilson G, Bryan J, Cranston K, Kitzes J, Nederbragt L, and Teal TK. Good enough practices in scientific computing. *PLoS computational biology* 2017; 13:e1005510. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1005510>
16. Goldberger AL, Amaral LA, Glass L, Hausdorff JM, Ivanov PC, Mark RG, Mietus JE, Moody GB, Peng CK, and Stanley HE. PhysioBank, PhysioToolkit, and PhysioNet: components of a new research resource for complex physiologic signals. *circulation* 2000; 101:e215–e220. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.CIR.101.23.e215>
17. Johnson AE, Bulgarelli L, Shen L, Gayles A, Shammout A, Horng S, Pollard TJ, Hao S, Moody B, Gow B, et al. MIMIC-IV, a freely accessible electronic health record dataset. *Scientific data* 2023; 10:1. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01899-x>
18. Johnson A, Bulgarelli L, Pollard T, Gow B, Moody B, Horng S, Celi L, and Mark R. MIMIC-IV (Version 3.1). PhysioNet. RRID: SCR_007345. 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.13026/kpb9-mt58>
19. Gow B, Pollard T, Nathanson LA, Johnson A, Moody B, Fernandes C, Greenbaum N, Waks JW, Eslami P, Carbonati T, Chaudhari A, Herbst E, Moukheiber D, Berkowitz S, Mark R, and Horng S. MIMIC-IV-ECG: Diagnostic Electrocardiogram Matched Subset. PhysioNet 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.13026/4nqg-sb35>
20. Strodthoff N, Lopez Alcaraz JM, and Haverkamp W. Prospects for artificial intelligence-enhanced electrocardiogram as a unified screening tool for cardiac and non-cardiac conditions: an explorative study in emergency care. *European Heart Journal-Digital Health* 2024; 5:454–60
21. Strodthoff N, Lopez Alcaraz J, and Haverkamp IV W. Mimic-iv-ecg-ext-icd: Diagnostic labels for mimic-iv-ecg (version 1.0. 1). PhysioNet. RRID: SCR_007345 <https://doi.org/10.13026/hdyc-1h77> 2024
22. Heil BJ, Hoffman MM, Markowetz F, Lee SI, Greene CS, and Hicks SC. Reproducibility standards for machine learning in the life sciences. *Nature methods* 2021; 18:1132–5. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01256-7>
23. Stodden V, McNutt M, Bailey DH, Deelman E, Gil Y, Hanson B, Heroux MA, Ioannidis JP, and Tauber M. Enhancing reproducibility for computational methods. *Science* 2016; 354:1240–1. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aah6168>
24. Read KB, Gibson G, Leahey A, Peterson L, Rutley S, Shi J, Smith V, and Stathis K. Understanding the challenges associated with finding and accessing restricted data in Canada: a mixed methods study. *FACETS* 2024; 9:1–9. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1139/facets-2023-0102>
25. Wilkinson MD, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg IJ, Appleton G, Axton M, Baak A, Blomberg N, Boiten JW, Silva Santos LB da, Bourne PE, et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data* 2016; 3:1–9. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
26. Collins GS, Moons KG, Dhiman P, Riley RD, Beam AL, Van Calster B, Ghassemi M, Liu X, Reitsma JB, Van Smeden M, et al. TRIPOD+ AI statement: updated guidance for reporting clinical prediction models that use regression or machine learning methods. *bmj* 2024; 385. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2023-078378>
27. Tanasković I, Lazarević LB, Knežević G, Milosavljević N, Dubljević O, Bjegojević B, and Miljković N. CardioPRINT: Biometric identification based on the individual characteristics derived from the cardiogram. *Expert Systems with Applications* 2025; 265:126018. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2024.126018>

28. Tanasković I, Lazarević L, Knežević G, Milosavljević N, Dubljević O, Bjegojević B, and Miljković N. Dataset for CardioPRINT-based Biometric Identification. 2025 Feb. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16919126>
29. DANS-KNAW. File formats. Accessed: 28.4.2026. 2026. Available from: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>
30. Kemp B, Värri A, Rosa AC, Nielsen KD, and Gade J. A simple format for exchange of digitized polygraphic recordings. *Electroencephalography and clinical neurophysiology* 1992; 82:391–3. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-4694\(92\)90009-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-4694(92)90009-7)
31. Kemp B and Olivan J. European data format ‘plus’(EDF+), an EDF alike standard format for the exchange of physiological data. *Clinical neurophysiology* 2003; 114:1755–61. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1388-2457\(03\)00123-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1388-2457(03)00123-8)
32. Moody G, Pollard T, and Moody B. WFDB Software Package. *PhysioNet* 2022 Jun. Version 10.7.0. doi: [10.13026/gjvw-1m31](https://doi.org/10.13026/gjvw-1m31). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.13026/gjvw-1m31>
33. DICOM Standards Committee. Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM). Accessed: 28.4.2026. National Electrical Manufacturers Association (NEMA). Arlington, VA, USA, 2026. Available from: <https://www.dicomstandard.org/>
34. Bidgood WD, Horii SC, Prior FW, and Van Syckle DE. Understanding and Using DICOM, the Data Interchange Standard for Biomedical Imaging. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 1997; 4:199–212. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1136/jamia.1997.0040199>
35. Wagner P, Strodthoff N, Bousseljot RD, Kreiseler D, Lunze FI, Samek W, and Schaeffter T. PTB-XL, a large publicly available electrocardiography dataset. *Scientific data* 2020; 7:154. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0495-6>
36. Wagner P, Strodthoff N, Bousseljot RD, Samek W, and Schaeffter T. PTB-XL, a large publicly available electrocardiography dataset. *PhysioNet* 2022. Version 1.0.3. RRID:SCR₀07345. doi: <https://doi.org/10.13026/kfzx-aw45>
37. Bousseljot R, Kreiseler D, and Schnabel A. Nutzung der EKG-Signaldatenbank CARDIODAT der PTB über das Internet. 1995. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1515/bmte.1995.40.s1.317>
38. Amato A and Di Lecce V. Data preprocessing impact on machine learning algorithm performance. *Open computer science* 2023; 13:20220278. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1515/comp-2022-0278>
39. Nešković ĐD, Tanasković I, and Miljković N. Feature selection for lying posture classification. *Book of Abstracts of The Third Serbian International Conference on Applied Artificial Intelligence (SICAAI)*. Kragujevac, Serbia: University of Kragujevac, 2024 :78–9
40. Frye M and Schmitt RH. Structured data preparation pipeline for machine learning-applications in production. *17th IMEKO TC* 2020; 10:241–6
41. Rangayyan RM and Krishnan S. *Biomedical signal analysis*. John Wiley & Sons, 2024
42. Trojani V, Bassi MC, Verzellesi L, and Bertolini M. Impact of preprocessing parameters in medical imaging-based radiomic studies: a systematic review. *Cancers* 2024; 16:2668. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers16152668>
43. Roh Y, Heo G, and Whang SE. A survey on data collection for machine learning: a big data-ai integration perspective. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* 2019; 33:1328–47. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TKDE.2019.2946162>
44. Sylolypavan A, Sleeman D, Wu H, and Sim M. The impact of inconsistent human annotations on AI driven clinical decision making. *NPJ Digital Medicine* 2023; 6:26. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-023-00773-3>

45. Rädtsch T, Reinke A, Weru V, Tizabi MD, Schreck N, Kavur AE, Pekdemir B, Roß T, Kopp-Schneider A, and Maier-Hein L. Labelling instructions matter in biomedical image analysis. *Nature Machine Intelligence* 2023; 5:273–83. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-023-00625-5>
46. Moody GB. Lightwave: Waveform and annotation viewing and editing in a web browser. *Computing in Cardiology 2013*. IEEE. 2013 :17–20
47. Cabitza F and Campagner A. The need to separate the wheat from the chaff in medical informatics: Introducing a comprehensive checklist for the (self)-assessment of medical AI studies. 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2021.104510>
48. Moody GB and Mark RG. The impact of the MIT-BIH arrhythmia database. *IEEE engineering in medicine and biology magazine* 2001; 20:45–50. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/51.932724>
49. Van Rossum G and Drake Jr FL. Python tutorial. Vol. 620. Centrum voor Wiskunde en Informatica Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 1995
50. R Core Team. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. Vienna, Austria, 2025. Available from: <https://www.R-project.org/>
51. Paszke A, Gross S, Massa F, Lerer A, Bradbury J, Chanan G, Killeen T, Lin Z, Gimelshein N, Antiga L, et al. Pytorch: An imperative style, high-performance deep learning library. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 2019; 32
52. Abadi M, Agarwal A, Barham P, Brevdo E, Chen Z, Citro C, Corrado GS, Davis A, Dean J, Devin M, et al. Tensorflow: Large-scale machine learning on heterogeneous distributed systems. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1603.04467* 2016. doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1603.04467>
53. Pedregosa F, Varoquaux G, Gramfort A, Michel V, Thirion B, Grisel O, Blondel M, Prettenhofer P, Weiss R, Dubourg V, et al. Scikit-learn: Machine learning in Python. *the Journal of machine Learning research* 2011; 12:2825–30
54. Hugging Face. Hugging Face Hub. Accessed: 28.4.2026. 2026. Available from: <https://huggingface.co/>
55. Higgins SG, Nogiwa-Valdez AA, and Stevens MM. Considerations for implementing electronic laboratory notebooks in an academic research environment. *Nature Protocols* 2022; 17:179–89. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41596-021-00645-8>
56. Shahriari M, Ramler R, and Fischer L. How do deep-learning framework versions affect the reproducibility of neural network models? *Machine Learning and Knowledge Extraction* 2022; 4:888–911. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/make4040045>
57. Moreau D, Wiebels K, and Boettiger C. Containers for computational reproducibility. *Nature Reviews Methods Primers* 2023; 3:50. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43586-023-00236-9>
58. Ince DC, Hatton L, and Graham-Cumming J. The case for open computer programs. *Nature* 2012; 482:485–8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature10836>
59. Rudin C. Stop explaining black box machine learning models for high stakes decisions and use interpretable models instead. *Nature Machine Intelligence* 2019; 1:206–15. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0048-x>
60. Barredo Arrieta A, Díaz-Rodríguez N, Del Ser J, Bennetot A, Tabik S, Barbado A, Garcia S, Gil-Lopez S, Molina D, Benjamins R, Chatila R, and Herrera F. Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI): Concepts, taxonomies, opportunities and challenges toward responsible AI. *Information Fusion* 2020; 58:82–115. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2019.12.012>
61. Lundberg SM and Lee SI. A unified approach to interpreting model predictions. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 30. 2017 :4765–74

62. Kapoor S and Narayanan A. Leakage and the reproducibility crisis in machine-learning-based science. *Patterns* 2023; 4. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2023.100804>
63. Lima EM, Ribeiro AH, Paixão GM, Ribeiro MH, Pinto-Filho MM, Gomes PR, Oliveira DM, Sabino EC, Duncan BB, Giatti L, et al. Deep neural network-estimated electrocardiographic age as a mortality predictor. *Nature communications* 2021; 12:5117. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-25351-7>
64. Rockenschaub P, Akay EM, Carlisle BG, Hilbert A, Wendland J, Meyer-Eschenbach F, Näher AF, Frey D, and Madai VI. External validation of AI-based scoring systems in the ICU: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making* 2025; 25:5. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-024-02830-7>
65. Seuru S, Grimm V, Barton M, Perez L, Gharakhanlou NM, Sengupta R, and Dagnino AM. The ODE (Overview, Data, and Execution) protocol for a standardized use of machine learning in environmental, social and related interdisciplinary sciences. *Environmental Modelling & Software* 2026 :106912. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2026.106912>
66. Strodthoff N, Wagner P, Schaeffter T, and Samek W. Deep learning for ECG analysis: Benchmarks and insights from PTB-XL. *IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics* 2020; 25:1519–28. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/JBHI.2020.3022989>
67. Moody GB, Muldrow W, and Mark RG. A noise stress test for arrhythmia detectors. *Computers in cardiology* 1984; 11:381–4
68. Liu X, Rivera SC, Moher D, Calvert MJ, Denniston AK, Ashrafian H, Beam AL, Chan AW, Collins GS, Deeks ADJ, et al. Reporting guidelines for clinical trial reports for interventions involving artificial intelligence: the CONSORT-AI extension. *The Lancet Digital Health* 2020; 2:e537–e548. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500\(20\)30218-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500(20)30218-1)
69. Kelly CJ, Karthikesalingam A, Suleyman M, Corrado G, and King D. Key challenges for delivering clinical impact with artificial intelligence. *BMC medicine* 2019; 17:195. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-019-1426-2>
70. Baker M. 1,500 scientists lift the lid on reproducibility. 2016. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/533452a>
71. Freedman LP, Cockburn IM, and Simcoe TS. The economics of reproducibility in preclinical research. *PLoS biology* 2015; 13:e1002165. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1002165>
72. Zwanenburg A, Vallières M, Abdalah MA, Aerts HJ, Andrearczyk V, Apte A, Ashrafina S, Bakas S, Beukinga RJ, Boellaard R, et al. The image biomarker standardization initiative: standardized quantitative radiomics for high-throughput image-based phenotyping. *Radiology* 2020; 295:328–38. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.2020191145>
73. Goldsack JC, Coravos A, Bakker JP, Bent B, Dowling AV, Fitzer-Attas C, Godfrey A, Godino JG, Gujar N, Izmailova E, et al. Verification, analytical validation, and clinical validation (V3): the foundation of determining fit-for-purpose for Biometric Monitoring Technologies (BioMeTs). *npj digital Medicine* 2020; 3:55. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-020-0260-4>
74. NeurIPS. NeurIPS 2021 Paper Checklist. 2021. Available from: <https://neurips.cc/Conferences/2021/PaperInformation/PaperChecklist> [Accessed on: 2026 Apr 21]
75. Hernandez-Boussard T, Bozkurt S, Ioannidis JP, and Shah NH. MINIMAR (MINimum Information for Medical AI Reporting): Developing reporting standards for artificial intelligence in health care. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 2020; 27:2011–5. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocaa088>
76. Klontzas ME, Gatti AA, Tejani AS, and Kahn Jr CE. AI reporting guidelines: how to select the best one for your research. 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1148/ryai.230055>

77. Arefeen A, Singh S, Razavi C, Ghasemzadeh H, and Dev S. Assessing the quality of reporting in artificial intelligence/machine learning research for cardiac amyloidosis. *JAMIA open* 2025; 8:ooaf104. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamiaopen/ooaf104>
78. Tanasković I and Miljković N. Kontrolna lista za primenu veštačke inteligencije u medicini [Checklist for the application of artificial intelligence in medicine]. Version v1. 2026 Mar. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19068928>
79. Center for Open Science. Open Science Badges. 2026. Available from: <https://www.cos.io/initiatives/badges> [Accessed on: 2026 Apr 21]
80. Lones MA. How to avoid machine learning pitfalls: a guide for academic researchers. arXiv preprint arXiv:2108.02497 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2108.02497>